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Commodification and Commercialisation of the Gospel in the 21st Century Church: The Nigerian Experience

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Abstract

The contemporary Nigeria churches have become money spinning ventures among ministers of God. Churches are becoming easy sources of financial gains where unsuspecting members are often exploited by those who are responsible for their spiritual nurturing. The Church is expected to be a refuge of comfort for the Christians in time of trouble and turbulent moments. It is rather unfortunate to observe that the Church has become an avenue for buying and selling of spiritual products, where miracles are commercialized, where money are being paid before you can receive your “blessings” or be prayed for by the so-called “men of God.” It is disheartening to say the least that ministers of God have commoditized and successfully commercialized the gospel by employing various means of marketing to advertise, brand and package gospel as a consumer or spiritual product to be sold and bought before life-challenges can be tackled. Sales of books and other spiritual items are common practices in the church today. The Church has become a place where sacred objects like rosary, rings, scapular, handkerchiefs, anointing oil, holy water are being commoditized and commercialized for material gains by “the men of God.” The intention of the paper is to examine how some charismatic ministers have shaped the religious-business environment and how their actions have impacted the genuineness of Christian

teachings in the contemporary Nigerian society. The paper also adopted qualitative method of research. The work concluded that Christianity should be a source of lifting burden rather than means of exploitation as being witnessed in Nigerian churches today. The paper recommended that ministers of God should adhere strictly to the instruction stated in Matthew, “freely you received, freely shall you give.”

Keywords: Commodification, Commercialization, Gospel, Church, Church Commercialization

Introduction

Churches in the contemporary Nigerian society are becoming money spinning venture owing get-rich syndrome and unhealthy competition among them. It has become a popular saying among Nigerians that one of the easiest ways of making it apart from being a politician and footballer is to establish a church and steady flow of income is assured. Unfortunately, a good number of these churches can be regarded as centres for exploitation and manipulation of innocent and desperate church members searching for miracles and answers to prayers.

It is glaring that a lot of church leaders in modern day Nigerian churches do merchandize the gospel for economic gains. They have succeeded in presenting the gospel in a deceitful way in their attempt to defraud and manipulate their members. Nwadiolor and Umeanolue (2013:56) noted that: Materialistic gospel message entered into Nigeria through the several visiting American materialistic gospel preachers and through their books, messages, magazines, pamphlets and radio programmes.... It is pertinent to say that commercialization and commodification of the gospel in Nigeria is characterized by increased abject poverty and other social vices like unemployment, armed robbery, bad leadership, kidnapping and a few others. Members of these commercialized churches are usually the poor, who want a way out of the level and who desired instant blessings on one hand and on the other hands are members who seek way of sustaining their wealth and who are also on the look-out for protection (Clarke, 2006: 15). One of the teachings of commercial churches is that financial breakthrough is a sign of God’s favour. Such teachings emphasis that God will make everyone materially rich. Thus, the best way of claiming these riches is to give to the church. By their actions, the ministers of God have turned the free gift of God to money-spinning venture through their commercialization

of consultation fees for prayers rendered on their behalf and the collecting of brown envelopes for prophetic offering.

Further scenarios that depict commercialization and commodification of the gospel can be illustrated fully “when adherents of the Christian faith pay for spiritual objects like candles, anointing oil, spiritual pen and pencils for success, and a host of others. The so-called “men and women of God” blatantly refused to heed to Jesus’ admonition of “freely you have received, freely you must give (Calvin, 2008:45).” Judging from the foregoing, the intention of this work was to examine the impacts of commercialization and commodification of the gospel on Nigerian Christianity and how the actions of the ministers of God engaging in such practices has continued to affect its growth.

Review of Related Literature

Church Commercialization

The phrase “church commercialization” denotes two things. In the first instance, it means the application of commercial principles in the running of the church or applying business principles to church administration or run it as a business with the goal of making financial gains (Nwanganga, 2015: 24). Secondly, it denotes the manipulation of the church, its services, with implied intensions to exploit members for economic gains (Galgoto, 2014: 47). It can also be described as conducting the church core mandate of soul winning, attending to spiritual and emotional needs of members with the sole aim of benefiting financially (Nwannganga, 2015: 32). Generally, commercialization of church should be conceived as every action, activity of church leaders, pastors, prophets that have economic making connotation.

Church

In the New Testament Greek, the word “church” is referred to as *ecclesia*, meaning an “assembly” (Jegede, 2016: 45). Similarly, in the Greek version of the Old Testament, the word *ecclesia* denoted the “gathering of the people for worship” (2016: 46). In the New Testament, it refers to a local Christian community. It is generally believed among the Christians that God founded the church through the work and deeds of Jesus and this is also sustained by the continual presence and activities of the Holy Spirit. Owing to this understanding, a church is described as a group of believers, associated together, under Christ, for His purpose (Zondervan Pictorial Encyclopedia

2314). However, the New Testament offers metaphors for the church. First, it describes the church as “body of Christ.” Second, the church is related to Christ as branches of a vine. A more intricate and pervasive relationship is implied by this image than by the image of the body. More importantly, it describes the church as the people of God; a description that stresses, on one hand, the continuity of the church with Israel and on the other hand, the church’s potential universality (Barth, 2013: 67).

Commodification

The term “commodification” is defined as treating something that cannot be owned or that everyone has a right to, like a product that can be bought or sold (www.dictionary.com). It refers to the transformation of goods, services, ideas, nature, personal information or people into commodities or objects of trade (Gill, 2008: 69). Therefore, commodification of the gospel means turning all Christian-related beliefs, teachings, symbols, sacred objects into products which can be sold for commercial gains. Thus, in Christianity, a commodity is “something to meet one’s particular needs at an acceptable cost to the person concerned” (Einstein, 2006: 21). People commoditize relationship when it is view as means to satisfy personal desires and agendas. Essien (2010: 6) identifies commodification of religion in faith branding, as a concept reflected in the packaging of religion as a product for purchase mainly using sacred objects and religious artefacts. Commodification, in religious parlance, refers to religious symbols becoming products, objects of consumption readily available in the “supermarket of religion,” in economic life and the media landscape (Ornella, 2013: 13). It is the process of re-contextualization of religious symbols, language and ideas from their original religious context to the media and consumer culture. In this process, religious symbols become commodities, objects of consumption readily available in the “supermarket of religion.” Based on the above, commodification of the gospel means turning church services into money-making activities where congregants have to pay money in order to receive healing or gain favour from God.

Commercialization

According to Wikitionary (en.m.wikitionary), commercialization is defined as the application of “business methodology to something in order to profit, the organization of something in a way intended to make a profit.” In the

same vein, the Oxford Dictionary (1092) describes it as “the process of running something or managing something principally for financial gains. There are two distinct views of the commercialization of the church. The one is a more positive appreciation of the “prosperity gospel” or the gospel of wealth and health, and the other, a more negative perspective that regards it as a practice that only benefits a few and leads to the abuse of followers.

Gospel

The word “gospel” is derived from the Anglo-Saxon term “god-spell,” meaning “good story,” a rendering of the Latin *evangelium* and the Greek *evangelion*, meaning “good news” or “good telling” (Ugwueye, 2002: 34). In the New Testament, the word refers to the announcement that Jesus has brought the reign of God to the world through his life, death and resurrection from the dead. In Christianity, the term “good news” refers to the story of Jesus Christ’s birth, death and eventual resurrection. According to Adelowo (2006: 11), gospel refers to the core doctrines and practices of Christianity. In a narrower sense, gospel means the message of salvation through faith in Jesus Christ. Outside of this application to religion, the word “gospel” is used to describe an idea or rule that is accepted as undoubtedly true. The Christian world in general, readily accepts the definition of the gospel as the good news about Jesus (Agbiji, 2015: 33), while others define Jesus’ offer of salvation through his death on the cross as the good news. Although both definitions are technically correct, yet, they fail to include several important facets of the good news which Jesus revealed to his children through additional scripture. In the context of this paper, gospel is used to imply Christianity and all that its entails including the teachings and practices of the adherents.

Origin of Commercialization and Commodification of the Gospel

Right from the Old Testament time, prophets like Amos, Micah and Ezekiel were against commercialization of religion. Prophet Amos, in particular, raised his voice in protest against the religious and moral corruption of his day by condemning exploitation and oppression of the poor and needy, corrupt and degenerate religious practices, perversion and corruption of justice and honesty as well as excessive indulgence and flagrant disregard for the law of God (Amos 2:8;5:4;1:5;11:8;4-6;6:12). The negative attitude of prophet Amos towards commercialization and commodification of the gospel

was manifested in the clash between him and Amaziah who refused to acknowledge in any way the divine sources of Amos' prophecies. Rather, he constantly and consistently referred to him as a political agitator. In the view of Ogunkunle (2006: 52), he opined that "the fact that Amaziah and other priests in Israel had commercialized religion is indicated in his derogatory advice to Amos, that he should go to Judah and 'earn' his bread there" (Amos 7:12). In the context of this work, "earning" could simply mean "services rendered and paid for." This therefore implies that to Amaziah and his fellow "professional prophets," religion and the free spiritual gifts of God were to be used for financial gains.

Similarly, Micah in his letters spoke against his listeners for their apostate lifestyle. Among the sins committed by them were perversion of worship practices, empty religious formalism (Amos 6:6-7), oppression of the poor and defenseless (Amos 2:2, 8-9), perversion of justice through bribery and dishonest business practices, idolatry and violence. As clearly stated in Micah 3:11; 6:11, religious leaders were charged of commercialization and commodification of religion because they collected money for religious services they rendered to people. Rather than serving and shepherding the flocks, the false prophets were actively engaged in leading the people astray. They were blinded by material gains they were getting from their innocent followers. To this extent, Shimazome (1998: 181) summed up the selfish attitude of such prophets thus: These leaders were giving the people false hope by telling them they would not be punished by God, that there would be no calamity. If someone paid the false shepherds well, they would pronounce peace on him. In other words, they told a person what he wanted to hear for a price.

Without doubt, these religious leaders were only concerned with their own welfare, their personal gains and comforts at the expense of the nation's welfare. Materialism and inordinate desire to get more was their goal, master and ultimate aim.

The same thing can be said of prophet Ezekiel. He was vehemently against the prophets and prophetesses who were into the business of commodifying and commercializing the gospel of Jesus. It is rather discouraging to know that commercialization of the gospel became more prominent in the New Testament era. It got to its peak even at the time of Jesus' earthly ministry as indicated in Matthew 21:12-13; Mark 11:15-18; and Luke 19:43-46. At a point in his ministry, Jesus expressed his indignation against the people

changing money and selling Doves in the temple. The Jewish temple authorities set up small booths where pilgrims could buy doves to sacrifice and where money could be changed. Those operating the booths were cheating the people and taking large profits for themselves. For this reason, Jesus drove them out and overturned their tables and benches. William (1954: 17) gave more insights into this phenomenon of selling Doves in the temple. Usually, every Jew had to pay a temple of one-half shekel a year. He further stated that the tax had to be paid in one particular coinage which means that the Jews that came from all over the world with all kinds of currencies had their money changed with exorbitant charge. This made the festive period a busy time for the temple authorities who were involved in the business of changing money rather than leading the people in the worship (1954: 23).

It is pertinent to mention that the business of gospel commercialization did not end in the temple or with the false prophets and prophetesses' activities. During the Feast of Passover, Ogunkunle (2006: 45) submitted that selling and buying of Doves became very popular and highly profitable. The organizers of the Feast of Passover strictly advised worshippers and those in attendant to buy doves at the temple stalls, often at exorbitant prices. These Doves could have been easily and cheaply purchased outside the temple, but the temple inspectors would be sure to find-fault or something wrong with them. Judging from the above, the exploitation meted out to the pilgrims by the Jew temple authorities, for their own financial gains, indicated that the pilgrims were not considered as worshippers but as things to be exploited. Jesus condemned this attitude and rebuked the religious leaders for the desecration of God's holy place. These scenarios depict commercialization and commodification of the church, and it should be seen as a violation of religious ethics.

Commercialization and Commodification of the Gospel in Nigeria

Weber (1989: 78) accentuated on the influence of religion on economic behavior. He submitted that the "spirit" preaches hard work and this produced discipline and rational pursuit of economic gains. It was believed that long before man was born, he was predestined to either salvation in heaven or condemnation in hell. This brought about anxiety. Thus, to relieve such anxiety, and resist temptation, man only has to exercise self-control and serious labour (Olawole, 2013: 21). To this extent, the church believes

that whether saved or condemned, the faithful must work hard for the glory of God. To them, hard work is a calling from God so as to establish His kingdom on earth. The purpose of hard work was to glorify God and that they should not spend their wealth on worldly pleasures, instead they invested in the preaching of the gospel.

However, in Nigeria today, the church seems to be deviating from this preaching. Churches do not preach hard work. Rather, they lay emphasis on “prosperity preaching.” Self-acclaimed ministers have turned Christianity into a huge business franchise marred by mischief. They carry out this act through various ways and forms. The commodification and manipulation of the gospel is played out in several ways by prosperity-minded gospel preachers. Instead of laying emphasis on dignity of labour and hard work, they have succeeded in twisting and upturning the concept of miracle and tithe that literally means 10% of one’s income. The innocent and unaware congregants are made to believe that once they paid 10%, their income will be doubled. They dwell on biblical portions that read thus, “he who sow sparingly will reap sparingly,” “you cannot sow maize and reap cocoyam,” “with your tithes and offerings you are robbing God,” to commercialize spiritual activities (Olawole, 2013 34). As a way of driving home manipulating intension, they often resort to the use of imprecation as threat (Achor, 2000 28). Among the churches in Nigeria, the use of divination is a common practice. Through this means, the prophets, prophetesses and pastors can predict the future, explain the present, and even uncover the past that is shrouded with mysteries for their “clients” and collect exorbitant fees for the supposedly religious services rendered. In this way, the church becomes a lucrative business venture.

More so, the prosperity preachers have been able to perfect several ways of commercializing the gospel for material gains. One of such ways is through the mounting of big billboards where they display catching and captivating themes of their supposed programmes during which special offerings and donations are collected. Captivating themes like, “*Osan Meta, Oru Meta* meaning literally “three afternoon three nights,” “Power must change hands,” “Fall and die,” and “power must change hands” are few of such themes often used to draw people’s attention to their programmes (Adewole, 2011: 72). A good number of them also print newsletters with exaggerated news and stories mainly to solicit for money. In the church today are vigorous advertisement of crusades and revivals and printed T Shirts

indicating the themes of the crusade are displayed for sales (Abogunrin, 2009: 76). However, some of these miracle healing pastors combined magical power with Christian faith. As such, quiet a lot of these miracles are mere fabrications intended to attract crowds and make money (Asaju, 1989: 91). It is disheartening to observe that commercialization of religion knows no bound in Nigeria. This is because everybody is allowed to self-licensed himself/herself as whatever and as a result, has golden opportunity to fool, deceive, lead or mislead unsuspecting members of the church (Jemiriye, 2012: 10). In the same vein, many gullible members just sink in whatever they are being fed by their religious leaders who simply take advantage of their gullibility and desperation to exploit them and amass wealth for themselves. Advance in communication and information technology have made many churches tech savvy. They use these new tools for further fund raising and managing the money, assets, records and crowds they are able to generate. As income of the church is booming so have opportunities for spending by crass commercialization and new technology (Nwanganga, 2018 28). In some churches in Nigeria, tithe payments are used as determinant factor for promotion of the pastors. The more money generated through tithe payment means the higher such pastors go in the hierarchy of the church. Pastoral visit has been turned into a clinic where people line up and pay consultation fees to see the pastor. Prayers are contracted for a fee which attracts a kind of prayer team to handle the prayer (William, 1954: 221). These materialistic tendencies of most Nigerian churches create a doubt in the minds of people concerning the real purpose of church.

Causes of Church Commercialization and Commodification on Contemporary Nigerian Churches

1. **Poverty:** Poverty has been considered as one of the major factors of church commodification and commercialization in Nigeria. Townsend (2011: 31), poverty is described as lack of opportunity to develop one's abilities and control one's own life owing to economic deprivation. Despite its abundance of human and natural resources, Nigerians still wallow in abject poverty. Speaking of poverty in Nigeria, it has been reported that 69.7% of Nigerians are living below the line of poverty. Over 80 million Nigerians based on the 120 million estimations survive on less than \$1per day. The growing rate of graduates in Nigeria as further increase the tension associated with poverty (The Punch 16). In

the attempt to suffer, many Nigerians find themselves in pastoral work even when it is obvious they did not receive any call from God. This explains the high rate of church commercialization in the contemporary Nigerian churches.

2. ***High Unemployment Rate:*** Unemployment is deemed as the greatest factor to the ever-increasing rate of proliferation. Nigerian streets are littered with churches. In every nook and cranny of the country are found newly established churches. One should not mistake this for spiritual growth of the people and neither should one misinterpret it as high level of spiritual consciousness of an average Nigerian. Rather, it should be attributed to the ever-increasing rate of unemployment being witnessed in the nation. Every year, the education sector keeps churning out graduates without corresponding employment plans for them. Owing to long search for gainful employment, many deserving graduates became frustrated and therefore resorted to pastoral work without receiving the call of God. Their taking to pastoral duties serves as means of livelihood. Some of them that possess oratory and good communication skills open ministries which later metamorphosed into full mega churches across the nation. This ugly situation apparently fans the embers of church commercialization. Although Nigeria is known throughout the world to have the largest number of churches (Jemiriye, 2009: 41), yet it has not positively helped in combating the various nefarious activities bedevilling the nation.
3. ***Poor Remuneration of Ministers:*** Poor remuneration, in this context means inadequate financial means of survival. As a mean of survival, people tend to develop several unethical behaviours or means without proper consideration of its effect on them and the society. The bane of church commercialization and commodification is also linked to the inability of most Nigerian churches to adequately cater for their ministers' welfare, more especially financially and materially. An extensive investigation carried out by Sunday Punch Newspaper (2017) revealed that many of the country's prosperity-preaching, super-rich mega churches pay their pastors poor wages. The Newspaper's findings revealed that a substantial majority of the pastors engaged by these churches, who are polytechnic and university graduates, earn between #25,000 to #45,000 a month. Some of the churches revealed were the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG), Living Faith World

Outreach, Mountain of Fire and Miracle Ministries, Deeper Christian Life Ministry, Christ Embassy International and Lord Chosen Charismatic Revival Ministries. In the attempt of the ministers in these churches to survive, other forms and ways are being devised and these may be in form of exploitation of church members, monetization of healings and prayers (Maduforo, 2025: 34). A pastor in one of the Redeemed Christian Church of God submitted that: The job of a pastor is a sacrificial one, no doubt, but what we are paid cannot ordinarily sustain us. The money is definitely not enough to meet our needs even with our access to loans and free accommodation provided by the church.

4. ***Inordinate Quest for Financial Benefits:*** Adonu (2019) in an interaction with Ekereoku observed that in Nigerian churches today, the greatest challenge preachers of God are facing is the quest for financial benefits through the spiritual services they are rendering to their congregants. Most of the ministers of God have lost focus on why they are in the ministry and their intention has shifted to material things. Churches, owing to quest for materialistic tendencies of the pastors, have been turned to commercial centres. Crusades are being organized on a daily basis with the primary goal of soliciting for money for personal benefits. The sacred objects have been turned to money spinning ventures through which easy money can be accrued. It must be clearly stated that God is not against having material goods. What God is against is “making material possession the centre of one’s existence.” This had led many ministers of God astray from the ministry entrusted into their hands and some are still being caught in the riptide that can carry them to the sea of worldly concerns.
5. ***Greed:*** Greed is an inappropriate attitude towards things of value, built on the mistaken judgment that “my well-being is tied to the sum of my possessions. Greed goes much further than money. A person can be greedy for money but also for fame, possessions, attention, compliments, gifts and much more (Hill, 2020: 23). In the Bible, the words greed, greedily, greedy, and greediness are always used to describe the selfish motivation of a person. Greed led to eternal condemnation of Gehazi, the servant of Prophet Elisha. Ahab coveted the vineyard of Naboth, and the end result was disastrous. In Nigeria today, commercialization of the church is a growing trend. There are

reported cases of embezzlement among the ministers of God of church funds. In fact, men of God now ask for gratification and charge outrageous amount for ministrations. Ecclesiastical corruption compounds the corruption in the nation, weakens the church and compromises her moral rights to speak against corruption in the nation. According to Monsignor John Aniagwu (2019: 19), Vicar General, Catholic Archdiocese of Lagos Episcopal Vicar, Ikeja Region, he submitted that ministers who are in the habit of commercializing the gospel are doing so at their own peril. In an interview with Moses Lucky Ogadi, Senior Pastor of Christ Elect Pentecostal Assembly (2019: 18), he condemned commercialization and commodification of sacred objects and concluded that churches who are into such acts are making merchandize of gullible persons and at the same time contradicting what Jesus Christ stood for during his earthly ministry.

Effects of Commercialization and Commodification of the Gospel on Nigerian Churches

- a. ***Exploitation:*** Commercialization and commodification of religious objects has become a common practice among charismatic leaders in Nigerian Christianity. In most cases, religious leaders take advantage of the vulnerability of their members for financial gain (Adabembe, 2024: 10). They mostly accomplish this through various means like ordering their followers to remove all money from their pockets during church services and such practices have drained and left a lot of the members stranded while the ministers enrich themselves at their expense.
- b. ***Distortion of Religious Values:*** It is unfortunate to observe that the binding principles of Christian teaching on love, brotherliness, compassion, fellowship, stewardship, peace and righteousness have been sacrificed on the altar of commercialization of the gospel by those saddled with the responsibility. Ministers of God in Nigerian churches have succeeded in converting revered customs into things that can be bought with money owing to their greed and excessive desire for money (Lovemore 2016: 27). The perversion of Christian principles has caused some to prioritize financial benefit over their overall spiritual growth.
- c. ***Conflict of Interest:*** Religious institutions now face conflict of interest due to commercialization of the gospel. In Nigerian churches today are

ministers of the gospel who put financial gain ahead of the spiritual growth of their churches and members. Therefore, they compromise the integrity of religious teachings in their pursuit of profit (Adabembe, 2024:11, 13).

Ways Out of Commercialization and Commodification of the Gospel on Nigerian Churches

In order to curb the excess of religious institutions, especially the nefarious activities of some men of God, and the commercialization of the gospel in Nigeria, it is high time the instituted authority started to regulate and license church leaders. This can be done by putting on ground strict laws against commercialization of religion and put a stop to abuse of people's believe system.

It is also expected of each church in Nigeria to pay attention to the welfare of her ministers. This is one of the ways they can be motivated to stick to their divine mandate, that is, to preach the gospel and direct souls to salvation and kingdom of God. When ministers of God have zero worries, commercialization of the gospel becomes a thing of the past. At this point, exhibiting their spiritual potentials for the upliftment of the church and individual church members becomes a matter of necessity.

Unemployment and poverty are two bedfellows that are very difficult to terminate. Unemployment gives room for poverty; the two social vices are major reasons for church commercialization. As a way of combating commercialization and commodification in the church, both government and private institutions should make it a point of duty to create employment opportunities for the teeming graduates. Soft loans can also be made available for those interested to start small scale businesses rather than depending on government jobs that are not forthcoming. This will go a long way in preventing people from dabbling into pastoral duties when it is clear to them that they were not call and neither do they have anything to offer spiritually.

In the attempt to curb commercialization of the gospel, various church associations and organizations (like CAN, PFN, CCN) are expected to wake up to their responsibilities of providing guidance and leadership by speaking and monitoring activities of affiliated churches and members of their religion. This is imperative because they are put in place to maintain religious sanctity and right doctrinal practices among their members. As a

measure of countering commercialization of the gospel, churches found wanting must be strictly placed under sanction as a deterrent for others. The get-rich syndrome is a big challenge among the Nigerian ministers of the gospel. Their inordinate desire for quick money has opened a flood gate for commercialization of the church. They have been able to play on the gullibility of members who desire solutions to one problem or the other. In order to prevent further abuse of the free gift of God, there is a strong need for re-orientation of church members. For instance, the fear of witches is a great force that drives people to seek spiritual solutions or deliverance from the spiritualists. Therefore, De-witching the minds of people is important to combating any attempt to commercialize the free gift. Sometimes, the fears of witches are unfounded and unnecessary. Prosperity-preaching pastors simply capitalize on the unsafe and fearful situation of people to trade their religion. It is, thus, essential for church members to develop the power of positive thinking that can drive away witches. By so doing, commercialization and commodification of the gospel will be effectively reduced if not permanently stamped out.

Conclusion

The history of commercialization and commodification of the church is as old as the practice of Christianity itself, if not older than Christianity. Recall that before the disciples were called Christians, commercialization of religion was an on-going practice in the temple among the Israelites and Jesus simply shown his displeasure towards it because the merchants valued it more than the religious activities. In the contemporary time, it has become a money-spinning business, the quickest way of making cool money at the expense of the church members. The implication is that church commercialization runs counter to church's tenets of sacredness, pure, holiness and Jesus' admonition of "freely you have received, freely you must give." The author maintains that God is not against church members giving genuinely to men of God without them demanding for such gratification as doing so will negate Matthew 10:8. Ministers of God should bear in mind that they were called by God to serve. Therefore, God will provide for their needs holistically and there is no need to be in fright mode.

Recommendations

The paper recommended that:

1. It is high time religious practitioners became regulated and licensed by governing authorities in order to curtail their excesses.
2. There is the need for both moral and ethical re-orientation for men of God. The ethical behavior of ministers of God must be in consonant with established conventions and church ethics.
3. They must maintain high level of professionalism in the calling. Professionalism must include a moral philosophy that governs behavior in a formal and systematic way leaving no room for ambiguity or confusion and that focuses on fairness, honesty, integrity, safety and authenticity as well as moral and legal propriety.
4. Church members must be encouraged to develop the power of positive thinking. This will go a long way in helping them combat the fear of uncertainty and also prevent them from becoming easy targets in the hands of prosperity-seeking pastors who are only interested in economic gains and who refer to them as “customers” rather than leading them to salvation.

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